

Unifying Spherical Force

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Abstract

This study proposes that gravitational attraction can be generated through simple flow vector composition. Experimental verification confirmed the actual generation of attractive force by this flow pattern.

Figure 1. Red: Intake vector, Blue: Exhaust vector

Figure 2. Resultant vector of Figure 1

Figure 3. Red: Intake x2, Blue: Exhaust x2

Figure 4. Resultant vector of Figure 3

References

- [1] Introductory physics: vector composition, conservation of momentum
- [2] Introductory mathematics: vector algebra

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Figure 5. Not bad

Figure 6. Ideal

Figure 7. Expected

Figure 8. Actual

Description

This prototype airflow generator can produce an airflow as shown in Figure 1.

Therefore, it is highly likely that a combined attractive force as shown in Figure 2 will be generated.

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Figure 9. Digital loadcell x8 experiment

Figure 10. Loadcell mounting detail

Result — 8-channel Loadcell Data

Loadcell: SC-616C 500g x8 | ADC: HX711 24bit x8 10sps

Baseline offset: +0.1 gf/ch (x8 = +0.8 gf)

Green zone: On1 (fan running). Red zone: OFF1.

Total (ch9): near-bottom t=6.1s, min=-20.7 gf @ t=10.1s. S/N = 662x (signal / noise std)

Loadcell plate: L20cm × H4cm t5 plywood | device distance r=10cm

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Figure 11. Module box detail (t5mm Plywood, 9x5cm, 8cm depth)

Figure 12. Fan: Wakefield Thermal DS0402812V2B-BT0 DC12V 2.34A

Figure 13. Side view: t2mm Polycarbonate + t40mm 4028 fan + t5mm Plywood = t47mm total space

Figure 14. Top view: 8-module arrangement inner $r=40\text{cm}$ outer $r=91\text{cm}$

3rd Party Replication Guide

[1] Base plate: 910x910mm t3 Aluminum composite panel (USD 45-70) [amazon.co.jp/dp/B0CCYHVCBW](https://www.amazon.co.jp/dp/B0CCYHVCBW)
alt: 4x4 plywood sheet 1x1m t5-10mm (USD 16)

[2] Top plate (observation): t2mm Clear Polycarbonate Sheet (USD 50-75) Clear is required for flow visualization.

[3] Fan (4028 server fan required): Wakefield DS0402812V2B-BT0 DC12V 2A (label 3.0A) 23W (my choice) ~USD 21 Delta PFB0412EN-E DC12V 2.6A 31.2W ~USD 19 1x ~USD 20 / 4x ~USD 80 / 8x ~USD 160 Note: 12V 1.0A or above required. 12V x 0.4A insufficient.

[4] Module box: Plywood 30x30cm t5mm

[5] M4 L45mm screw x8 (supporting top plate) + L20 Coupling Nuts (height adjustment)

[6] Attention: module units radius R must be over 30cm. $\times R=20\text{cm}$ — not working (short loop field, no effect on outer area) $\sim R=30\text{cm}$ — marginal $\checkmark R=40\text{cm}$ — recommended Too small R (20cm) may cause a closed internal flow loop with no force reaching outside.

[7] 3D printed module: OK! (Prototype not yet made)

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Derivation

General: $F_g = m_{in} * v_{in} * \sin\theta_{in} - m_{out} * v_{out} * \sin\theta_{out}$

Mass conservation: $m_{in} * v_{in} = m_{out} * v_{out}$

Energy conservation: $v_{in} = v_{out}$ (from $E \propto v^2$)

Simplified: $F_g = mv(\sin\theta_{in} - \sin\theta_{out})$

Result: $F_g \propto \Delta\theta$

Cases

$\theta_{in} > \theta_{out} \rightarrow F_g > 0$ attract 90/0 $\sim +9.8 \text{ m/s}^2$ D/S Direct in / Spiral out

$\theta_{in} = \theta_{out} \rightarrow F_g = 0$ neutral 90/90 0.0 m/s^2 D/D or S/S

$\theta_{in} < \theta_{out} \rightarrow F_g < 0$ repel 0/90 $\sim -9.8 \text{ m/s}^2$ S/D

Max efficiency (D/S: $\theta_{in}=90^\circ$, $\theta_{out}=0^\circ$)

1.0 - 0.0 \approx eff 1.0

$F_g = mv(\sin\theta_{in} - \sin\theta_{out}) = mv * 1.0 = mv$

almost all Qin flow momentum can be converted to Fg

Flow density (Qm: mass flow rate)

$Q_m \propto m$

$Q_m(in) = Q_m(out)$

$Q_m(in)(r1) = Q_m(in)(r2) = Q_m(out)(r1) = Q_m(out)(r2) = Q_m(in/out)(rn)$

$S = 4\pi r^2$

amount of local flow $\propto Q_m(r) / S \propto r_{const} / r^2$

Novelty of this model

$F_g \propto \Delta\theta$ — unique idea as far as known.

Other theories: Fatio / Le Sage (Δv) or sink (Δmv)

sink = source loop

sink + source + $\Delta\theta$ model: not found in literature search.

Le Sage (Δv) \rightarrow energy loss / overheating problem.

Sink only (Δmv) \rightarrow energy loss (overheating) ++ fluid mass loss.

$\Delta\theta$ efficiency is already an established human technology.

Uses only established physics — no unknown or unestablished effects assumed.

Search similar: 'sling angle', 'crane angle'

Vertical arm (90°) $\rightarrow 1.0 \times$ spec

Horizontal arm (10°) $\rightarrow 0.1 \times$ spec

Vertical sink flow (90°)

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Figure 15. USF calc vector simulator

Figure 16. earthsim_v14 dual-mode spiral sim

Figure 17. flow_physics_V209 my experiment sim

Figure 18. Analog experiment sequence: start → run → end

Description

Figure 15: High school physics / math → an unreported attractive force field is generated. Let's try!

Figure 16: Emulates real Earth's gravitational field by spiral gravity flow. Some patterns cause gravity and others do not — you can see it easily. Let's try!

Figure 17: CFD-like reproduction of my experiment: 1, 4, 8 module test. Spiral exit flow occurs when phase shift button is turned on. Reproduction accuracy is very high.

Figure 18: Loadcell (digital) experiment already showed a positive effect, but result may come from program error — so additional analog method was tested: car run test. Same attractive effect observed. Not a digital program error. This car has 0.4 gf static friction.

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Figure 19.

Figure 20.

Figure 21.

90°: 26.7 gf (100%)
sin 90° = 1.000

60°: 24.6 gf (92.1%)
sin 60° = 0.866

45°: 18.4 gf (68.9%)
sin 45° = 0.707

30°: 12.8 gf (47.9%)
sin 30° = 0.500

Almost accurate – Tilting weakens 90° direction force

sin90° = 1.0 / sin0° = 0.0

Figure 22.

Description

Figure 19: "Apple falling toy" driven by $\Delta\theta \rightarrow$ causes F_{diff} ($F_{down} - F_{up}$)

Figure 20: Multi-stage flow bending around module — no artificial bend plate needed

Figure 21: Spiral field = attractive field / Direct in / Spiral out (D/S mode) $\theta_{in}=90^\circ$ $\theta_{out}=0^\circ$

Figure 22: Flow θ experiment by kitchen scale — horizontal flow has less effect on pushing the scale down

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Conclusion

A circular attractive force field was observed using simple flow vector sum.
No prior reports found. Third-party replication encouraged (USD 20~300).
Hard to correlate with heat, electromagnetic force, or vibration.

References

- [1] Introductory physics: vector composition, conservation of momentum
- [2] Introductory mathematics: vector algebra

Data Availability

All data and files are available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19396050>

AI Tools

Claude (Anthropic) was used for graph generation, simulation development, and document formatting assistance. All experimental design, measurements, theory, and conclusions are the author's own.

Conflict of Interest

None.